

Book Review

Kate Pahl and Jennifer Rowsell, *Living Literacies: Literacy for Social Change*
MIT Press, 2020; 312 pages

Cary Bazalgette

Independent researcher on children and moving-image media
Honorary Research Fellow, UCL Institute of Education
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9137-1023>

Soon after Sumerian merchants and officials started keeping notes on clay tablets about their transactions and administration, debates must have occurred about who should have access to this useful new system and how best to teach it to novices. Five thousand years on, the same debates continue to flourish. It is widely assumed that for most of history, literacy was confined to elites, but recent scholarship demonstrates that the role of literacy in many ancient societies was much more complex, and systems of writing evolved for various purposes at different times and in different parts of the world. Archaeologists differ about when and where trading began and when some groups started living in permanent settlements; probably at different times and places throughout the Upper Paleolithic period (i.e. between 50,000 and 12,000 years ago (Graeber & Wengrow, 2021). But whenever these changes happened, sooner or later people needed methods of recording transactions, quantities, measurements, agreements and laws, while sacred signs and symbols became an important way of helping to maintain religious beliefs and practices.

In his editorial introduction to the book *Ancient Literacies*, Johnson argues that “the moment seems right ... to try and formulate more interesting, productive ways of talking about the conception and construction of “literacies” in the ancient world – literacy not in the sense of whether 10 percent or 30 percent of people in the ancient world could read or write, but in the sense of text-oriented events embedded in particular social contexts” (Johnson, 2009, p. 3). In justifying this turn, Johnson cites Grillo, Heath and Street (Grillo, 1989; Heath, 1983; Street, 1984) as the originators, respectively, of the terms “literacy events”, “literacy practices” and “communicative practices”

– terms that Pahl and Rowsell enthusiastically adopt in this book. All three of these terms attempt to capture a way of thinking about literacy that can characterise and illustrate what “embedded in particular social contexts” actually means. From a historical perspective, this is clearly an important insight. Reading, writing and arithmetic were not simply invented by elites for their own use and advantage, but grew up originally through social practices such as buying, selling, loaning and renting; storing and sharing foodstuffs; negotiating agreements about land cultivation, ownership, boundaries and buildings; marriages and inheritance; child-rearing; rituals and celebrations; story-telling, jokes, tricks and performance.

Despite the enormous differences between 21st-century cultures and those of up to fifty thousand years ago, we can still recognise the social practices listed above as related to our own. We can understand that some form of literacy must have played a role in them, and still does. When cultures became larger, wealthier and more complex, and many-tiered class structures and more complex administrative systems developed, literacy became an essential administrative tool. Education therefore became a key route to employment and social advancement, and by the end of the 19th century many societies had made it compulsory for all children. But from at least as far back as the 17th century, thinkers and activists including people such as Comenius, Locke, Rousseau, Pestalozzi, Fröbel, Tagore, Dewey, Steiner, Montessori and Freire had disputed the form that education should take, challenging authoritarianism and rote-learning. All of them argued for the importance of learners’ own experience as the starting-point for education, which of course included the social practices of their families and communities. In the UK, writings by Richard Hoggart, Harold Rosen and others provoked rethinking amongst some academics and progressive educators, about how education could better relate to learners’ everyday lives (Hoggart, 1958; Richmond, 2017). Questions about what literacy is or should be were central to these arguments.

In the 20th century, the industrialisation of information and entertainment media and the accelerating development of new production and distribution technologies led to demands from some people for a broader focus in literacy teaching, to include forms of communication and expression that had become significant in children’s lives: film, television, comics, popular music, magazines. In the UK for example, these arguments led to optional examination courses in Film Studies and Media Studies being offered to 16- and 18-year-olds. The British Film Institute (BFI) campaigned successfully for references to “media” (including film and television) to be included in the requirement for English in the first (1988) version of the National Curriculum. The National Literacy Strategy (NLS), set up by the new Labour Government in 1997, had radical ambitions (Stannard, 2007) and collaborated with the BFI to develop resources

and teacher training that could enable film study to be taught in primary schools. But when a Conservative government came to power in England in 2010, much of these developments were lost, and literacy teaching was forced back once again into an Arnoldian curriculum (see <https://blogs.ucl.ac.uk/ioe/2013/06/21/the-best-that-has-been-thought-and-said/>). Struggles for literacy to be more widely defined and for literacy teaching to be more learner-centred have been happening since the mid-20th century, and many of the ideas that underpinned have been circulating for at least three centuries. So those who seek to take up these arguments again ought to recognise that they are not initiating a new struggle. Pahl's and Rowsell's brand of radicalism dates back only to the 1990s.

Gunther Kress's keynote at the Toulouse conference, *New Directions in Media Literacy* (Bazalgette, Bevort, & Savino, 1992) outlined his approach to what he called "multimodality", based on analyses of print and image layouts in school textbooks, to illustrate his claims for the "dominance of the image" and for the importance of "design" in human communications. In 1994 the New London Group (NLG) of mainly North American academics (but including Kress) started to publish arguments for rethinking literacy and literacy teaching, elaborating the concepts of multimodality and design, which they link together by proposing that there are six "design elements" in the meaning-making process: linguistic, visual, audio, gestural and spatial meanings relate to each other through the patterns of meaning provided by the sixth element, the multimodal (Cope & Kalantzis, 2000). Surprisingly, this was not a way of broadening the concept of "text" to include moving-image media; their concern was with "visual images and their relation to the written word, e.g. visual design in desktop publishing or the interface of visual and linguistic meaning in multimedia" (p7).

That was how digital technologies were referred to in 1994, but the tsunami of technical and communication innovations that followed the arrivals of Facebook in 2004 and the iPhone in 2007 turned "multimodality" into a workhorse term that has been stretched well beyond its inferential capacity. David Buckingham and I have discussed the problematic ways in which it has been used in academic and educational contexts (Bazalgette & Buckingham, 2013). The same has happened to "literacy": Wikipedia's "Literacy" page now lists appropriations by ten different fields as indicating (rather than defining) a desired level of competence and/or awareness, and there are probably many more. And according to Ofcom, "media literacy" is now nothing more than "staying safe" (see <https://davidbuckingham.net/category/media-literacy/>).

The NLG's central mission in seeking to place social practices at the centre of debates about literacy was to emphasise that "meaning is an active and dynamic process, and not something governed by static rules". One might wish to question whether "meaning" can ever be

called a “process”, but in the excitement of radical change there is always a tendency to challenge established definitions. This certainly characterises Pahl and Rowsell’s project from the start. They begin their book by asking “What is Living Literacies?” (the singular verb form here is presumably to alert us to the possibility that “living” as used in their title could have both adjectival and verbal functions, as well as showing us that static rules can easily be broken at will).

Each of the six main chapters of *Living Literacies* is headed by a verb in the gerundive form. So, seeing, disrupting, hoping, knowing, creating and making are meant to function as “key lenses through which we describe and structure our living literacies approach”. In each chapter one or more “research projects” are described, although the term “research” is used somewhat loosely, since we are not told what the research questions or findings are. The projects involve, for example, teaching an unspecified number of 11-15-year-olds how to fish, in Rotherham over a two-year period; working over a two-month period with eleven adults afflicted by poverty, mental health problems or addiction, who attended a community centre in the Niagara region, enabling them to take photographs of anything other than human beings; working in a Manchester primary school with 8-9-year-olds over a three-year period to help them research what “odd” means, the outcomes being a coproduced set of films and “Odd Boxes” and observations of children engaging with a playground pirate ship constructed by one of the research team.

Each of these projects sounds interesting and unusual, and might possibly have revealed something about the nature and roles of literacy – or literacies – in diverse contexts and social practices, involving varied and probably innovative pedagogies, if we could see the research reports, and if there are any. Apart from the interviews that are quoted in some chapters, and the illustrations throughout (unfortunately in black and white), the book’s purpose is not so much to recount the research activities themselves but to ponder their meaning and draw out ideas about how literacies might be re-imagined (though almost totally ignoring forms such as film, TV, computer games, apps, social media). The result – regrettably – is a vague and unsatisfying ramble through a succession of statements and claims, avoiding structured argument and explanations of relationships through recourse to words such as “entwined”, “entangled”, “braided”, “interwoven” and just “woven”. This metaphoric theme may have feminist motivations, but it does nothing to clarify the arguments.

Despite the book’s democratic aspirations its language is often obscure or, more often, merely vague. A central concept in the book is the “literacy event”, (taken from Shirley Brice Heath and from Brian Street) but constant re-workings make its definition increasingly vague and overburdened with neologisms. For example:

A creative approach to the literacy event offers a felt and embodied way in to thinking about literacy, one that considers possibilities and furtherness and opens the way to “new-ness.” Seeing the literacy event in this way creates a new kind of feeling about its event-ness” (p. 122).

The book ends with “A Call to Action for Literacy Education”, starting with references to narrowly prescriptive official curricula and ending with a requirement that “educators and literary policy makers [must] become attuned to a conceptual framing of literacy as lived. Our hope is that, if they do, the emergent, messy stuff of literacy will become part of the experienced moment-by-moment unfolding of the literacy event” (p. 166).

Let us consider for a moment what it means to ignore the boring old basic skills of reading and writing and what illiteracy, in the old-fashioned definition, actually means for most people. In a world where 63% of the world’s illiterate adults are women, where the route to higher socioeconomic status is almost always accessed by people who are literate at least in the basic reading-writing-and-arithmetic sense, where illiteracy bars access to knowledge about hygiene and nutrition and to ensuring that children live beyond the age of five, much of Pahl’s and Rowsell’s argument reads as dangerously self-indulgent. Of course most of us in education are angry about the narrowness of the curriculum and our target-driven education system. Of course we argue for more respect towards children and their relentless desire for learning, and for recognising the diversity of social practices, religions, ethnicities, abilities, gender identities and cultures. But to achieve these on a large-scale means focused advocacy and a hard slog towards political change. Entwining and entanglement won’t help.

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